

Clustering glacier behavior

A multi-variate time series clustering approach

Fabian Kainz, MA
Data Science & Intelligent Analytics
FH Kufstein
Kufstein, Austria
2110837802@stud.fh-kufstein.ac.at

ABSTRACT

Glaciers are an indicator for global climate change. Increasing temperatures have a substantial impact on the world's glacier inventory. Shrinking glaciers impact geographical regions and societies as a whole. Monitoring glacier behavior, therefore, is a critical task for different fields in natural sciences. Machine learning models are commonly used for inventorying glaciers using computer vision and classification. The current paper introduces a clustering model to identify similar behavior of glaciers around the world. Clustering glacier behavior can guide further research activities to focus on a specific cluster of glaciers or inform decision making processes about similarities. The proposed model, based on a sample of 200,000 glaciers, introduces three clusters of glaciers showing different behavior over time. The model uses multi-variate time series analysis and considers changes of a glacier's area, volume and thickness of ice.

CCS CONCEPTS

•Computing methodologies ~ Machine learning ~ Learning paradigms ~ Unsupervised learning ~ Cluster analysis

KEYWORDS

Climate change; Glacier; Machine Learning; Clustering; Glacier inventorying

1 Introduction

Glaciers are commonly used as indicator for global climate change [8]. The increasing temperatures over the last decades are a threat for glaciers mass balance and ultimately affect the lives of millions of people around the world. Declining glaciers cause serious issues for many societies by impacting the transboundary hydrological cycle causing related issues, such as irrigation, energy production, and natural hazard prevention [7] as well as rising sea-levels [17]. Therefore, monitoring the behavior of glaciers and glacier shrinkage over time is a crucial activity to develop and adapt strategies in affected regions. The foundation of monitoring glacier behavior is solid baseline documentation. Such documentation can help to raise awareness for climatological changes. A prerequisite for this kind of documentation is a sound focus on consistency and long-term data

retrieval [7]. One initiative focusing on collecting and storing ongoing glacier changes is the World Glacier Monitoring Service (WGMS). Established in 1986 from a merger of the two former ICSI services PSFG (Permanent Service on Fluctuations of Glaciers) and TTS/WGI (Temporal Technical Secretariat/World Glacier Inventory), the WGMS collects the following standardized data on glaciers around the world through observation [15]:

- changes in mass, volume, area and length of glaciers with time (glacier fluctuations)
- statistical information on the distribution of perennial surface ice in space (glacier inventories)

The current paper aims to develop a clustering model to classify glaciers based on the data collected over the past years. Glaciers with similar behaviors over the past years will be collected in one cluster. This enables decision makers around the world to better plan and carry strategies to mitigate the risks for society.

The first section of the paper will introduce the basic terminology used throughout the paper and summarize related research. Within the second section the dataset is described. Section three describes the model as well as the pipeline used. In section four the results of the clustering are presented and discussed. Moreover, the findings are summarized and critically reflected for its implications for further research.

2 Theoretical Background

After defining the terminology used throughout the paper related research is presented.

2.1 Terminology

The terminology used in this paper is adapted from [5] and [15] and described below.

Glacier is a persistent mass of ice and snow.

Mass balance can be measured for a point or glacier-wide. It describes the mass/volume of the (part of the) glacier at any given time. Usually mass balance is measured for a year or a season.

Thickness describes the distance between the surface of the glacier and the underlying ground. Thickness is ideally measured using a dense array of point measurements. The term is closely

related to mass balance. Thickness can change due to ablation (i.e. melting and calving), accumulation (i.e. snowfall) or the compaction of snow.

Area is the spatial area covered by the glacier. Compared to mass balance, and thickness, it neglects the underlying mass and is measured by projecting the glacier margins (outlines) onto a planar field.

Elevation is the vertical distance between a point and a baseline. Usually, sea level is used as baseline but for earlier measurements there is a missing alignment. A synonym for elevation is altitude.

Front is the lowest point of the glacier. It is the frontline of the glacier margin which separates the glacier from ice-free terrain.

2.2 Related Work

The application of machine learning techniques in the field of glacier monitoring is not new. There is an extensive body of literature acknowledging the advantages of machine learning or deep learning techniques to tackle challenges arising from climate change and glacier shrinkage.

[3] presents a comparative study where three machine learning algorithms are tested for their suitability to estimate area and volume of glaciers in Columbia. The study concludes that all three algorithms under investigation (Support Vector Machine, Random Forest, Maximum Likelihood Classification) perform well on satellite image classification.

Extensive research is carried out in the field of debris covered glaciers. Debris on the surface of a glacier can hinder detection and monitoring. [2] tests a new automatic classification scheme for hierarchical mapping of glacier surfaces based on machine learning classifiers. The study suggests the usage of Random Forest Classifiers (97% accuracy on test set). Other studies put effort into the selection of the right features [14]. More sophisticated deep learning architectures for mapping of debris covered glaciers are introduced with models like GlacierNet2, which provides complete glacier outlines at regional scales, including accumulation and ablation zones [16].

Resulting models are often used for glacier inventorying. [6] introduces a U-Net model and applies it to Austrian glaciers. Other studies use glacier outline detection to derive area and mass balances from already available satellite images [4, 11].

While current studies mainly focus on the detection of glacier outlines and classification based on satellite images, the current study uses the inventory received from these measurements in tabular form to classify glaciers based on their behavior over the past years.

3 Glacier monitoring data

The dataset retrieved from [15] consists of multiple tables and measurements for 215.036 glaciers. The proposed clustering model is based on measurements between 2000 and 2021. The current section describes the available data with an in-depth focus on the data used for classification. The first table presented below introduces the different data tables and their content.

Table 1: Description of data tables

Dataset	Description
GLACIER	General and most likely static information about each glacier.
STATE	Glacier length, area, and elevation range.
CHANGE	Measured changes in glacier thickness, area, and/or volume.
FRONT_VARIATION	Glacier length changes from measurements.
MASS_BALANCE_OVERVIEW	Overview of glacier mass balance surveys.
MASS_BALANCE	Glacier mass balance measurements by elevation band.
MASS_BALANCE_POINT	Glacier mass balance measured at specific points.
SPECIAL_EVENT	Extraordinary events concerning glacier hazards and dramatic glacier changes.

Measurements in different tables describing the behavior of one glacier are identified using the WGMS_ID of a glacier. Based on the results of an exploratory data analysis, a subset of features extracted from the datasets is selected. The current analysis focuses on clustering glaciers based on their behavior over time. Therefore, clustering is performed mainly using time-related features like changes measured over time. The features presented in table 2 are selected:

Table 2: Description of features

Feature	Description
AREA_CHANGE	Change in area (1000 m ²) for the elevation band.
THICKNESS_CHG	Mean change in ice thickness (mm) for the elevation band.
VOLUME_CHANGE	Change in ice volume (1000 m ³) for the elevation band.

Looking at the features selected for two randomly selected samples shows different behavior over time. *Adler* is a single lobe glacier located in the Rhone basin in Switzerland while *Abano* is a glacier located on Georgia with a well-defined catchment area. The figure below shows their respective cumulative development of thickness since 2004.

Figure 1: Comparison of changes in volume from two glaciers

While the *Abano* glacier increased in thickness, the *Adler* glacier showed a massive decline. Most glaciers (over 95%) within the dataset at hand show declining values for most features (area, thickness, volume).

4 Clustering pipeline

The clustering pipeline is built using *Kedro*, “a framework for creating reproducible, maintainable and modular data science code” [1]. While *Kedro* provides the backbone for preprocessing, modelling and evaluation, the clustering is performed using *tslearn*, a library specialized on time series modelling supporting multivariate time series modelling. Besides utility functions for preprocessing input data, *tslearn* provides algorithms for clustering. This paper uses *tslearn*'s KMeans clustering and dynamic time warping (DTW) [12].

4.1 Preprocessing

During preprocessing data is loaded from the different tables described above. After selecting only important features, the loaded data is merged using the WGMS_ID and a respective year. At this point, the data represents the cumulative changes measured for each glacier for each year. To apply multivariate time series clustering, the data is reshaped into a multi-dimensional array (shape: number of glaciers, number of years, number of features). Figure 2 below shows the visualization of the preprocessing pipeline.

Figure 2: Visualization of the preprocessing pipeline [1]

4.2 Modelling

The time series data from the preprocessing pipeline above is consequently used for modelling. Since the proposed clustering algorithm (KMeans) is prone to different scales [9], the time series input is scaled. Now, that all data is prepared for modelling, a KMeans clustering algorithm is applied to find suitable clusters within the data.

4.2.1 KMeans

Clustering is the task of grouping similar objects together. Similarity is measured based on the distance within different characteristics of any observation. The KMeans algorithm calculates distance using traditional distance metrics (i.e. Euclidean distance) within the same characteristic and try's to minimize the sum of distances within each cluster [10].

4.2.1 Dynamic time warping

Due to shifts in time series data, traditional distance metrics fail to cluster time series' based on underlying trends. To overcome this limitation, distance metrics dedicated to time series, such as DTW are introduced. DTW optimizes distance from different time series of length *n* and *m* using the optimization problem stated in figure 3 below:

$$DTW(x, y) = \min_{\pi} \sqrt{\sum_{(i,j) \in \pi} d(x_i, y_j)^2}$$

Figure 3: Optimization problem of DTW [12, 13]

DTW clusters time series data based on their shape rather than their mathematical distance at given points [13].

The following figure shows the visualization of the modeling pipeline.

Figure 4: Visualization of the modeling pipeline [1]

5 Results, discussion & future work

The model was trained using different configurations and input features. A priori assumptions lead to three clusters focusing on the features measuring change. Including categorical features like the form of a glacier or its location lead to a model with high weights on those attributes. Therefore, the proposed clustering model is based on the changes in thickness, area and volume over time. Yet, many glaciers only had one or even no measurement and were removed from the dataset. The three clusters defined by the model can be interpreted as follow:

- **Cluster 0:** There is a moderate decline in all change related features. There are peaks for thickness and volume which led to massive declines within some years.
- **Cluster 1:** While there are no changes measured for area, there is a moderate decline in all other change related features.
- **Cluster 2:** Moderate behavior of volume changes with some outliers (broad confidence interval). The area of glaciers dropped significantly within the past two years. Thickness of ice also experienced volatile development.

Figures 5-7 show the behavior of the three change related features over time. They also indicates measurement peaks for certain features within a couple of years (i.e. volume was measured mainly between 2000 and 2008).

Figure 5: Behavior of volume by cluster

Figure 6: Behavior of area by cluster

Figure 7: Behavior of thickness by cluster

The shifts of change shown in figure 5-7 indicate, that not all glaciers have measurements for all features in every year. It is subject to further research to determine the impact of this imbalance on the clustering model. It also remains open, whether categorical features such as the form or location of a glacier can enhance the models performance. Approaches for dimensionality reduction can also contribute to better performance.

Besides the limitations and subjects for further research mentioned above, the results presented can be used as a foundation to tailor interventions to protect the worlds glacier inventory. Successfully applied interventions for a glacier within a cluster can be transferred to other glaciers within the same cluster. Moreover, the results allow decision makers around the world to form alliances and tackle the issue of glacier shrinkage on a global scale.

NOTES

The source code of the used pipeline for data preprocessing and modelling as described in section 4 is available in the following GitHub repository:

https://github.com/fabiankay/glacier_clustering

The coding was done by the main author of the current paper.

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